

RETHINKING SUCCESS IN DIGITAL BUSINESS MODELS: ENGAGEMENT-IMPACT TENSIONS IN YOUTH SMARTPHONE USE

Workshop Paper

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Abstract

Digital business models often define success through engagement, retention, and growth. Yet youth smartphone use reveals a central tension: the same engagement mechanisms that create business value may also contribute to adverse societal outcomes among young users. This paper proposes a direct-indirect impact perspective on IS research. Direct impact refers to the intended contributions of research across academia, business, and society. Indirect impact refers to how research may shape the technologies, business models, design principles, and success logics that subsequently affect these same areas. Using youth smartphone use as an illustrative case, the paper argues that impact-oriented IS research must critically examine both forms of impact. It further suggests that GenAI-augmented practitioner-focused literature reviews can help synthesize fragmented evidence across disciplines and translate it into stakeholder-specific guidance for developers, parents, schools, and regulators.

Keywords: Types of impact, digital business models, impact tensions

1 Introduction

Research on digital business models has often sought to generate academic impact by advancing our understanding of the value creation mechanisms underlying such models, including network externalities, adoption dynamics, user engagement, and platform-based scaling (Parker et al., 2016; Steininger, 2019; Zott et al., 2011). Extant research has also aimed to create business impact by offering normative guidance for designing successful digital business models (e.g., Machado et al., 2024; Weill & Woerner, 2013), as well as societal impact by studying regulatory challenges associated with digital businesses and platform-based market structures (e.g., Clemons & Madhani, 2010). Benbya et al. (2026) conceptualize these forms of impact across three areas: academia, business, and society. Their framework is valuable because it helps IS research reflect on how different impact strategies may primarily contribute to one or several of these areas.

However, while these distinctions are highly useful for organizing the direct impact of IS research, they do not fully capture a second and equally important dimension: the indirect impact of IS research through the technologies, concepts, design principles, and digital business model logics that we study, explain, optimize, or legitimize. I therefore argue that impact-oriented IS research should distinguish between two intertwined but analytically distinct forms of impact. Direct impact refers to the intended contributions that IS research makes across academia, business, and society. Indirect impact, by contrast, refers to the ways in which IS research may shape the concepts, technologies, digital business models, and success logics that subsequently produce effects across these same impact areas. In this sense, direct impact is closer to intended or authored impact, while indirect impact is closer to downstream impact. Direct and indirect impacts may align, but they may also diverge. In such cases, impact becomes not only a matter of producing relevant research, but also a matter of understanding how the technologies and success logics we study create tensions across academia, business, and society.

Youth smartphone use provides a particularly illustrative case for such tensions. Engagement-oriented digital business models often create business value by maximizing attention, usage, retention, and network effects within smartphone-based ecosystems. From a business perspective, such engagement can be interpreted as a central success condition of digital business models. IS research may therefore generate positive academic impact by improving our understanding of smartphone-based business models and positive business impact by identifying design principles and success factors for such models. At the same time, however, the very mechanisms that support engagement may contribute to adverse societal outcomes among vulnerable young users, including loneliness, depression, sleep problems, or eating-related concerns (Twenge et al., 2018; Xiao et al., 2025; Yoo, 2024). Thus, research that helps explain or improve engagement-driven business models may also have indirect impact by contributing to the broader technological and managerial logics through which such engagement is designed, optimized, and scaled.

This creates a paradoxical situation. Impact-oriented IS research may support academic knowledge creation and business success while indirectly contributing to technologies whose societal effects are ambiguous, contested, or harmful. This tension can be understood through the lens of paradoxical IS theorizing. Wang et al. (2026) distinguish between different meanings of paradox, including “spear-shield” paradoxes, which refer to situations in which conflicting pathways of action appear simultaneously reasonable but undermine one another. Engagement-oriented digital business models illustrate such a spear-shield tension: increasing engagement is desirable for business model success, but the same engagement logic may undermine societal goals related to youth well-being, sleep, and healthy development. Thus, the question is not only how digital business models create value, but also how their success logic generates direct and indirect impact tensions across academia, business, and society.

These impact tensions are difficult to identify because relevant knowledge is often fragmented across disciplines. IS research may focus on digital business models, engagement mechanisms, platform ecosystems, or regulation, while psychological, medical, educational, and communication research may examine negative outcomes of smartphone and social media use among young people. As a result, IS scholars may only see part of the overall impact landscape. This fragmentation is particularly problematic when indirect impacts unfold beyond the disciplinary boundaries within which IS research is typically conducted and evaluated. Understanding such indirect impacts requires synthesizing evidence across domains that do not always share concepts, methods, or outcome measures. This is precisely where new forms of evidence synthesis become important. Generative AI (GenAI) now creates opportunities to identify, extract, cluster, and synthesize large and interdisciplinary bodies of literature that would previously have been difficult to process at scale. Used responsibly, GenAI can therefore help uncover indirect impact pathways beyond traditional IS boundaries. It can support researchers in tracing how digital technologies and business model logics affect different stakeholders and impact areas, thereby enabling a more comprehensive understanding of engagement-impact tensions. Yet GenAI should not be understood as a substitute for scholarly judgment. Rather, it can support human-led synthesis processes that remain grounded in source validation, interpretation, and theoretical reflection. I argue that practitioner-focused literature reviews are particularly suitable for this purpose (Block et al., 2025). Such reviews can help IS researchers synthesize fragmented evidence on the direct and indirect impacts of digital technologies and translate it into actionable implications for different stakeholder groups, including developers, parents, schools, and regulators. In this way, practitioner-focused reviews can transform knowledge about technology-related indirect impact into direct research impact.

To summarize, this paper argues that impact-oriented IS research needs to think impact twice: as the direct impact of research across academia, business, and society, and as its indirect impact through the technologies, business models, and success logics that IS research helps to explain, optimize, or legitimize. I use youth smartphone use to illustrate this argument because engagement-driven business models create value while contributing to potential negative societal outcomes. Although the direct-indirect impact distinction applies to IS research more broadly, digital business model research is particularly revealing because it theorizes and legitimizes success logics such as engagement, retention, scaling, monetization, and network effects.

I further argue that GenAI-supported practitioner-focused literature reviews (Block et al., 2025) can help identify such impact tensions and translate cross-disciplinary evidence into stakeholder-specific guidance. In doing so, the paper contributes to ongoing discussions on how IS research can become more impact-oriented in times of complex societal challenges.

2 Direct and Indirect Impact in IS Research

Rather than limiting impact to scholarly publications and citations, recent work has emphasized that IS research can create value across multiple domains. Benbya et al. (2026), for example, distinguish between three major impact areas: academia, business, and society. Academic impact refers to contributions to theory, concepts, methods, and cumulative knowledge. Business impact refers to the ways in which research informs managerial decision-making, organizational practice, digital innovation, and business model design. Societal impact refers to research contributions that address broader public, social, regulatory, ethical, or policy-related concerns. This distinction is highly useful because it expands the scope of IS research impact beyond academia. It also helps researchers reflect on the intended audience and purpose of their work. Some research projects may primarily contribute to academic debates, whereas others may be designed to influence business practice, policy, or societal discourse. In this sense, impact-oriented IS research requires researchers to ask not only whether their work is rigorous and relevant, but also for whom it is relevant, what kind of change it seeks to enable, and under what conditions such change may occur.

However, I argue that the impact of IS research cannot be fully understood by looking only at the intended and direct contributions of research. IS research often studies technologies, digital infrastructures, platforms, algorithms, business models, and design principles that themselves shape organizations and society. Research may therefore influence the world not only directly through publications, recommendations, teaching, policy advice, or practitioner guidance, but also indirectly through the technological concepts and success logics it helps to shape, optimize, legitimize, or critique.

I therefore propose a distinction between direct and indirect impact of IS research. Direct impact refers to the intended contributions of IS research across academia, business, and society. This includes, for instance, theory development, methodological innovation, managerial guidance, design principles, policy recommendations, or stakeholder-oriented advice. Indirect impact, by contrast, refers to the ways in which IS research may shape the technologies, digital business models, design assumptions, and success metrics that subsequently produce effects across these same impact areas. In other words, IS research does not only have impact by informing stakeholders; it may also have impact by shaping the technological and organizational arrangements that later affect stakeholders.

Direct and indirect impacts may align, but they may also diverge. Research on engagement, adoption, personalization, or platform growth may create academic and business impact, while indirectly supporting design logics that intensify usage, attention capture, or dependency among vulnerable users. Such tensions are particularly visible in engagement-driven digital business models, where engagement supports retention, data generation, advertising revenues, and network effects, but may also contribute to excessive use, sleep disruption, attention fragmentation, or social comparison. This resonates with recent work emphasizing that digital technologies often produce both bright-side and dark-side effects (Schoormann et al., 2025).

Impact logic	Academia	Business	Society
Direct impact of IS research	Builds knowledge about digital business models, engagement mechanisms, network effects, and smartphone ecosystems	Provides guidance for designing, scaling, and managing engagement-oriented digital business models	Translates evidence into recommendations for parents, schools, regulators, and public debate
Indirect impact of IS research through researched technologies and success logics	Reinforces or challenges assumptions about engagement, adoption, and usage as desirable research outcomes	Legitimizes design choices that optimize attention, retention, personalization, data generation, and monetization	Contributes to technologies and usage environments that may affect youth well-being and development

Table 1. Direct and indirect impact of IS research in engagement-oriented digital business models.

Following Wang et al. (2026), this tension can be understood as a spear-shield tension: increasing engagement may be both economically rational and societally problematic. A direct-indirect impact perspective therefore extends existing discussions of IS research impact. It does not replace the distinction between academic, business, and societal impact, but adds a second analytical layer.

The first layer asks where research creates impact: in academia, business, or society. The second layer asks how research creates impact: directly through its intended contributions, or indirectly through the technologies, concepts, and business model logics it helps to shape. Table 1 summarizes this two-layer perspective and applies it to engagement-oriented digital business models.

Combining both layers allows IS researchers to better understand why impact-oriented research may itself be paradoxical. This perspective also clarifies the role of literature reviews in impact-oriented IS research. If indirect impacts are distributed across technologies, disciplines, stakeholder groups, and outcome domains, they are difficult to identify from within a single research stream. Practice-oriented literature reviews can therefore serve as mechanisms for tracing, synthesizing, and translating such indirect impacts. By integrating evidence across disciplines and organizing it for different stakeholder groups, such reviews can transform knowledge about indirect technology impacts into direct research impact.

3 Engagement-Impact Tensions in Youth Smartphone Use

Youth smartphone use provides a salient case for examining direct and indirect impact tensions in IS research. Smartphones have become always-on infrastructures through which platform-based business models, social media, games, messaging services, video platforms, and algorithmically curated content are continuously accessible. In this ecosystem, user engagement is a central success metric. High levels of usage, frequent checking, retention, and interaction generate data, strengthen network effects, increase advertising revenues, and improve opportunities for personalization. From a business model perspective, such engagement mechanisms are economically rational. IS research that explains adoption, engagement, personalization, or platform growth may therefore create direct academic impact by advancing theory and direct business impact by informing the design of successful digital business models. However, the same mechanisms may also contribute to indirect societal impacts when embedded in the everyday smartphone use of children and adolescents. The literature on youth smartphone use points to several negative outcome domains, including mental health problems, sleep disruption, attention and academic difficulties, social and family conflicts, and physical health concerns (Twenge et al., 2018; Xiao et al., 2025; Yoo, 2024).

Importantly, these outcomes do not necessarily result from smartphone use per se, but from specific constellations of access, usage contexts, engagement patterns, mechanisms, and vulnerability conditions. Smartphone access and usage patterns include screen time, checking frequency, late-night use, multitasking, and bedroom access. Usage contexts include social media, gaming, messaging, short-form video, and general internet use. Mechanisms include problematic or addictive use, social comparison, fear of missing out, sleep displacement, attention fragmentation, cyberbullying exposure, and displacement of offline activities (Kelly et al., 2018; Twenge et al., 2018; Xiao et al., 2025). Vulnerability and protective conditions include age, gender, self-control, self-esteem, baseline mental health, parental mediation, family context, and school rules (Yoo, 2024).

This synthesis is based on an ongoing AI-augmented practitioner-focused review of 162 papers on negative outcomes of youth smartphone use. Rather than presenting the full review, I use it here as an illustrative evidence base for the broader argument: negative outcomes are not caused by smartphones per se, but emerge from constellations of access, engagement mechanisms, usage contexts, and vulnerability conditions. Youth smartphone use therefore illustrates a spear-shield tension (Wang et al., 2026): engagement is economically valuable and analytically central for digital business models, yet the same engagement logic may undermine societal goals related to youth well-being, sleep, attention, and development. The challenge for impact-oriented IS research is not simply to reject engagement, but to rethink how engagement can be designed, limited, redirected, or governed in ways that account for societal consequences.

4 Practitioner-Focused Reviews as an Impact Pathway

The case of youth smartphone use illustrates that indirect impacts of IS research are difficult to identify when relevant evidence is distributed across disciplinary boundaries. Research on digital business models, platform ecosystems, engagement mechanisms, and network effects is often located in IS and management research. In contrast, research on youth well-being, mental health, sleep, attention, family conflict, or developmental vulnerability is often located in psychology, medicine, education, communication, or public health. As a result, IS researchers may understand the value creation mechanisms of digital business models without fully seeing their broader societal consequences.

This is where AI-augmented cross-disciplinary reviews become relevant for impact-oriented IS research. By enabling the power for synthesizing evidence from fields beyond IS that examine societal consequences of the same digital systems, such reviews can make visible what often remains outside the immediate scope of IS research: how engagement-oriented technologies affect vulnerable users in practice. I argue that practitioner-focused literature reviews can serve as an important impact pathway in such contexts (Block et al., 2025). Their purpose is not only to summarize academic knowledge, but to translate fragmented research into actionable insights for stakeholder groups that can respond to the problem. For youth smartphone use, this means translating evidence into guidance for actors who shape different parts of the engagement-impact tension, including developers, parents, schools, and regulators.

Generative AI can expand the potential of such reviews by supporting the identification, extraction, clustering, and synthesis of large and interdisciplinary bodies of literature (Malik & Terzidis, 2025). It can help researchers process evidence across fields that would otherwise remain fragmented or only partially visible from within IS. In this sense, GenAI may increase the speed and breadth with which indirect impacts of technologies can be traced and translated into direct research impact. However, GenAI does not remove the need for scholarly judgment. It may accelerate synthesis, but it cannot decide which evidence matters, how findings should be interpreted, or how tensions between business value and societal harm should be governed. Therefore, GenAI-augmented practitioner-focused reviews (Block et al., 2025) should be understood as human-led synthesis processes in which GenAI supports, but does not replace, critical interpretation. Thus, GenAI-supported reviewing can become an impact mechanism when it helps IS research jointly consider direct and indirect impacts: not only how research informs stakeholders, but also how the technologies and success logics studied by IS research produce indirect (potentially unwanted) downstream societal consequences.

5 Conclusion and Questions for Impact-Oriented IS Research

This paper contributes to the IIS workshop discussion by proposing a direct-indirect impact perspective on IS research. Building on the distinction between academic, business, and societal impact, it argues that IS research creates impact not only through its intended contributions, but also indirectly through the technologies, business models, design principles, and success logics it helps to optimize, legitimize, or critique. Youth smartphone use illustrates this tension. Engagement-oriented digital business models may generate business value through attention, retention, and network effects, while the same engagement logic may contribute to adverse societal outcomes among young users. Thus, what counts as success from a digital business model perspective may become problematic from a societal perspective. GenAI-augmented practice-oriented literature reviews can help make such tensions visible by synthesizing fragmented evidence across disciplines and translating it into stakeholder-specific guidance for developers, parents, schools, and regulators. This opens a central question for IIS research: How can we create direct research impact while critically reflecting on the indirect impacts of the technologies and success logics our research helps to shape?

This question also requires rethinking my own position as a scholar of digital entrepreneurship and digital business models. If research on digital business models helps clarify how engagement, retention, and scaling create value and business success, it may also contribute to the diffusion of precisely those success logics with their downstream indirect impacts. The point is not that such research should stop, but that impact-oriented IS research must treat this indirect contribution as part of its responsibility and further elaborate on the indirect impacts that it might spawn.

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